

Predicting Student Performance with Control-flow Graph Embeddings

John Marsden
North Carolina State
University
jmmarsde@ncsu.edu

Spencer Yoder
North Carolina State
University
smyoder@ncsu.edu

Bitu Akram
North Carolina State
University
bakram@ncsu.edu

ABSTRACT

Existing AST-based techniques for embedding student code have been used to help represent student understanding of programming concepts. However, though these embeddings capture syntactic information about student code submissions, they can miss semantic information like code flow through looping structures and conditionals. To address this limitation, we embedded Control Flow Diagrams of student programming submissions, which include semantic information. For our first evaluation of this technique, we verified that the Euclidean distance between embeddings corresponds to human-evaluated code similarity. Then, we evaluated the effectiveness of this technique for student performance modeling by using these vectors to predict student performance at the end of the course. During our evaluation, we found that our CFG-based embedding approach outperforms our baseline methods by a minimum of 7% when predicting student performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Good methods of representation for student programs are critical for student modeling in introductory programming courses. They are critical because they allow for the creation and development of tools, such as automated tutors, which rely on machine learning algorithms [14, 5]. Many current representations rely on techniques that focus on the actual text of the program and the syntactic information of the program [17, 3]. However, student programs contain rich structural and semantic data that goes beyond the raw text and syntactic information. This semantic information is important to understanding the purpose and validity of a piece of code. We suggest that it could also be important to modeling students' current knowledge state.

Recently, within the software engineering and educational data mining communities, there has been much work in representing programs through the use of *embeddings* [3, 17, 2, 6]. Embedding is a process of compressing input into a dense vector representation which encodes important prop-

erties and relationships.

Embedding can be performed by extracting the intermediate state of a machine learning model which compresses an input in order to make a prediction. A popular method for embedding is Skip-Gram, which uses machine learning to predict the *surrounding context* for an input (for example, the surrounding words in a sentence for an input word). After training, the Skip-Gram model will then be able to generate an internal state for each input which can be used as the embedding.

Modern *code* embedding techniques fall into two categories. Static techniques, which use artifacts that can be obtained without the code ever running, and dynamic techniques, which use artifacts created by the code's execution. Many static techniques utilize source code directly [11] or abstract syntax trees parsed from the source code [3, 17]. This means these techniques can be used on code that does not compile and, in the case of any pure source code techniques, may not be parseable. Conversely, dynamic techniques rely on logged program states [20, 16] or machine instruction execution traces. This gives them a better look into the semantics of the program code but requires a longer amount of time to run and requires that a program be compilable. So, a potential method to improve the performance of static techniques is to embed a data structure from static analysis work that explicitly contains the semantic information that can be extracted by dynamic techniques.

One such data structure is **control-flow graphs** (CFGs). CFGs represent data about the possible logical paths that a program can flow through utilizing a graph structure. They allow for the capture of information about the flow of a program as well as the encoding of some semantic information not typically explicitly accessible through AST-based techniques. We hypothesize that the use of CFGs for embedding can provide more utility for student modeling than AST-based embedding techniques by explicitly encoding semantic information. To evaluate our hypothesis, we compare the results of CFG-based code embeddings with the results of utilizing a state-of-the-art AST-based embedding technique, Code2Vec, while predicting students final performance.

In this project, we aim to answer the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** Can embeddings of control-flow graphs effec-

tively encode program features in an educational context?

- **RQ2:** Can embeddings created from control-flow graphs outperform AST-based methods in predicting students' performance?

2. BACKGROUND/RELATED WORK

2.1 Student Performance Modeling

Predicting student success using programming data is becoming a widely studied field in educational data mining [27, 13] with the goal of improving instruction for students in computer science classes, where there is a dearth of direct, one-on-one instruction and an increased need for such instruction among students. Methods for predicting student success based on early grades [1], automatically identifying knowledge components [24], and providing automated feedback [10] are being created and applied for the purposes of educational tools such as automated tutors [12].

2.2 Representing Code

Representing code is a difficult problem [17] that is particularly relevant to computing education (CEd). Since programs come in the form of source code and/or abstract syntax trees (ASTs) we are unable to leverage many of the ML techniques available to us directly. So, we must design transformations for these representations such that we can leverage more of the tools available.

Many static and dynamic analysis techniques have been created for usage in the field of compilers and optimization. These techniques have since been leveraged for use in software engineering research and educational data mining to generate code representations.

One popular representation is pairwise tree edit distances. By taking the ASTs of two programs, you can calculate exactly what changes must be made to convert this program to another program. This representation is particularly useful in constructing hints but is still not widely supported by techniques easily available and grows linearly with respect to the amount of data available. Clustering is one way of decreasing the state space that you have to search through and techniques defining methods of comparing programs using a specialized control-flow representation combined with clustering have shown promise in providing feedback. [17]

A powerful form of code representation is code embeddings [3, 17, 2, 6]. Researchers have been able to use these embeddings to summarize code [17], predict method names [3], identify programming errors [16, 25], and identify program functionality [16].

Some common static techniques used to generate embeddings leverage information about the ASTs for a program. The idea is that ASTs provide a program-agnostic method to analyze the programs in comparison to methods that look at the code prior to its' conversion to an AST. Some of these techniques, such as AST2Vec, create an embedding by analyzing the entire tree. Others, such as Code2Vec and Seq2Vec, create embeddings of smaller components and aggregate them together to embed the entire tree.

One well-known static technique is Code2Vec[3]. Code2Vec was developed by software engineers for the task of method name prediction. It is a neural model which trains an embedding matrix for *path contexts* from the ASTs in the dataset. A path context is defined as the path through the closest common ancestor between two leaves of the abstract syntax tree. Figure 1 shows how these path contexts are weighted using an attention mechanism and summed to create embeddings for methods. The Code2Vec model is trained to predict method names with these features, which can be extracted from the model as embeddings. It has since been used for student modeling purposes by Shi and Price [25].

Figure 1: The Code2Vec architecture [3].

Dynamic techniques, such as those proposed by Cleuziou and Flouvat [7] and Paaßen et al. [16] rely on analyzing either instruction traces or variable traces. These techniques are able to leverage the extremely rich data available to the systems running the code such as machine instruction traces, memory dumps, etc. They collect information that is able to identify program strategies, identify when a program is running incorrectly without intensive test suites, and identify where errors might be in the code.

2.3 Control-flow Graphs

Control-flow graphs (CFGs) are an intermediate representation commonly used in static analysis for compiler optimization and dead-code-finding techniques. They are directed graphs where each node represents a *basic block* and each edge represents a jump in the control flow to another basic block. A basic block is a series of instructions or statements that do not have any labels that a jump can target or a jump instruction. The CFG representation allows compilers to identify certain classes of issues in a program (such as infinite loops or unreachable code) because the representation contains semantic information about the flow of the program in the paths that exist. Other static analysis techniques such as code2vec [3] and ast2vec [17] in EDM do not contain as much information about semantics. The only way to collect this semantic information is through dynamic analysis. However, this has the problems noted in section 1.

CFGs also allow us to compare two different programs which

may utilize similar techniques but contain different code. For example, the usage of a while loop versus a for loop. In an AST, these are completely different trees. In a CFG, depending on the chosen representation, they can be exactly the same (an example is provided in section 3.2). This is both a strength and a weakness. This allows us to easily compare visually different code and identify semantic similarities. However, this can remove important distinguishing features from the original source code. For the purpose of student modeling, this technique may hide whether or not a student has learned how to use the desired construct. For example, using a for loop as opposed to using a while loop like a for loop.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data

We utilized the CodeWorkout dataset from the 2nd CSEDM data challenge. This dataset contains 154949 convertible programs from 780 students in an introductory university computer science course over the Fall 2019 and Spring 2020 semesters. Submissions were written in Java for 50 problems, each of which allowed for multiple submissions. Each submission includes the student’s code, compilation results, and score based on unit tests. Every program is short, containing one or two Java methods. This dataset also contains the final exam scores for each student.

To generate CFGs with the CFG generator discussed in Section 3.2, any programs input into the generator had to meet certain pre-conditions. First, the programs had to be parsable. Second, the programs could not contain `try/catch` blocks and `throw` statements as representing such flow was outside of the scope of this research. Third, the programs had to meet a certain level of compilability to be converted if it contained a `foreach` loop. If any of these preconditions were not met and the CFG generator failed to convert the program, we removed that code state from our embedding training data.

Final exam grades in the first semester were reported in the range 0-1. In the second semester, they were reported in the range 0-100. So, we normalized the grades to use the same scale by dividing the second semester grades by 100.

When training the models, we randomly divided the dataset into training and test sets by students. This division, as opposed to submissions, was chosen because there was only one final exam score per student and we predicted students’ final exam scores. 80% (624) of the students were placed into the training group and the remaining 20% (156) were placed into the testing group. All of our models using the embedding methods were only trained using submissions made by the students in the training group and then the models performance was validated with the testing split. The distribution for the grades in each group is shown in Figure 2. Students with no exam score in the data set were given a score of zero.

3.2 Generating Control-flow Graphs

To generate control-flow graphs from student code, we took advantage of the rich ecosystem of static analysis tool libraries that already exist. First, we started by using the

Figure 2: Grade distributions for train and test students. Train mean (std): 0.59 (0.25), Test mean (std): 0.61 (0.23)

`javaparser`¹ library to convert the students written methods into ASTs. These are only the methods and not the students’ entire programs because the dataset only contains students’ methods. After we had the ASTs, we used the built-in Visitor pattern functionality in `javaparser` to build a CFG using the `JGraphT`² library. Our CFG differs from typical CFGs, like those used with compilers, as it represents every single statement in the source as a vertex whereas most CFGs collect every statement in a block of code into a single node.

We chose a finer granularity in the representation of the program as a CFG in order to create embeddings which better capture relationships between programs. The graph embedding techniques we adopted rely on embeddings for each node. The less information there is in a single node, the more likely it is to find the same node in multiple CFGs, so by reducing the amount of information in a node, we increase the likelihood that each graph can be comprised of the same core components.

To generate the CFGs,

1. We extracted the ASTs from every individual method in our dataset. If a code submission had multiple methods, we split it into multiple ASTs and produce individual graphs for each one.
2. For each AST, we converted each statement subtree into a single node and added it to our control-flow graph.

¹<https://javaparser.org/>

²<https://jgrapht.org/>

Figure 3: On the left, we have a for-based aggregation loop. On the right, we have a while-based aggregation loop. In the center, we have the control-flow graph that both programs generate. Each statement and conditional is highlighted and labeled with their corresponding statement in the control-flow graph. This is the same as the statement and conditionals in the other loop.

3. We connected each node with the next node in the program execution together with edges (containing no value) indicating the path of execution that program execution will follow when that particular node is run.
4. We created decision nodes for each decision statement that were in the AST. `if` statements, ternary expressions, `switch` statements, `for` and `foreach` loops, and `while` and `do-while` loops produce decision nodes. However, `for` and `foreach` loops are a special case and produce not only decision nodes, but also several statement nodes of their own. Our node creation process does not include exception flow.
5. We add both a true and false edge to every decision node indicating which path a programs' execution could follow. A true or false edge denotes the path a program will follow when the expression that the decision node contains evaluates to its respective value. Both a true and a false edge must be created for every decision node.
6. Finally, we implemented three separate canonicalization strategies. For the first strategy, we canonicalized all names and literals in the graphs to either VAR if it is a variable, or the name of the type followed by `_LIT` if it is a literal (for example, `INT_LIT`). For the second strategy, we canonicalized only the variables. For the third strategy, we perform no canonicalization at all.

For an example of the CFGs generated by our first canonicalization strategy, see Figure 3.

3.3 Embedding Graphs

There is a wide body of research using and developing methods of embedding nodes in graphs based on their local topology [8]. These methods have been used successfully to reconstruct graphs as well as predict hidden edges. Several are available in a downloadable library for use [23]. We adapted implementations of two methods, DeepWalk and Node2Vec. We chose these methods for their simplicity and ease of adaptation. In the future, we plan to refine our method with more sophisticated graph embedding techniques, such as Graph Neural Networks [22].

3.3.1 DeepWalk

DeepWalk [19] is a graph embedding technique which embeds the nodes in a network using random walks and the Skip-Gram Word2Vec model [15]. Figure 4 shows the DeepWalk architecture. A directed graph is fed in as input to the model. For each node, the model performs N random walks of length L (both N and L are hyperparameters of the DeepWalk model). A random walk is a sequence of nodes, where each node is the randomly chosen neighbor of its predecessor in the sequence. A Skip-Gram model is trained on the set of all random walks. In this way, random walks are analogous to sentences in Word2Vec and each node is analogous to a word. This model can then generate embeddings for each node in the graph.

Figure 4: The DeepWalk Architecture. The red path shows a valid random walk.

3.3.2 Node2Vec

Node2Vec [9] is an adaptation of the DeepWalk model that introduces variable probabilities to the random walks in an attempt to prioritize the preservation of each node’s *local neighborhood*. Figure 5 shows how two additional hyperparameters, p and q , control the probability each node will be added to the random walk. If v is the latest node in the walk and t is the prior node, the walk will add t with probability $\frac{1}{p}$. Neighbors of v that are also neighbors of t are added with probability 1. Neighbors of v that are not neighbors of t are added with probability $\frac{1}{q}$.

After probabilistically generating random walks for every node, Node2Vec creates node embeddings using a Skip-Gram model, just like DeepWalk.

Figure 5: p and q in the Node2Vec architecture. This figure is from Grover and Leskovec’s paper [9]

3.3.3 Embedding Control-flow Graphs

We had to modify DeepWalk and Node2Vec to process our data. One limitation of these two embedding approaches is that they are designed to create node embeddings for a single network. To overcome this limitation, instead of running the models on each graph individually, we used a set of random walks from all graphs to train the Skip-Gram model.

Furthermore, in order to capture syntactic information from the programs, we treated each node’s *contents* as a word in Skip-Gram instead of its *id*, which is the default method for these graph embedding techniques. Figure 6 shows our adaptations to DeepWalk and Node2Vec for creating embeddings for each unique statement from the CFGs. After creating these embeddings, we represented each graph, G as

$$\sum_{n=1}^{|G|} v(G_n)$$

where $|G|$ is the number of nodes in G , G_n is node n in G , and $v(G_n)$ is the embedding for node n .

3.4 Baseline AST-based Model

We evaluate our models against Code2Vec [3], as a representative AST-based program embedding model. We chose Code2Vec as a near-state-of-the-art method which outperformed other models at the task of predicting method names [3] and been used previously in an educational context [26, 25]. We trained a new model, using the tools from the

Figure 6: Our modifications to DeepWalk and Node2Vec which train on random walks containing program statements.

Code2Vec GitHub repository ³ to generate embeddings for every submission made by the students in the training group.

3.5 Calculating Program Similarity

We first evaluated our embeddings against Code2Vec by using Code2Vec, DeepWalk, and Node2Vec to calculate program similarity. In order to evaluate this, we manually selected two pairs of exercises that utilized similar programming concepts: Exercise 1, Exercise 2, Exercise 3, and Exercise 4. Exercise 1 and Exercise 2 both require the usage of multiple nested if statements containing boolean expressions like `||`, perform comparisons with other variables, and both return integers. Exercise 3 and Exercise 4 require if statements as well but require comparisons with literals instead and are not using any boolean expressions. They also return either booleans or strings but not integers. We chose these exercises to test similarity between submissions to a single exercise and similarity between submissions to similar exercises. We hypothesized that, for the vectors obtained from submissions for these problems, the submissions for a single problem would be close together, the submissions for two similar problems would be further away, and the submissions for two dissimilar problems would be even further away.

For each problem, we randomly selected 10 correct (score=1) submissions from the entire dataset and plotted the Euclidean distance for each pair of the 40 submissions in a heat map. We generated heat maps for Code2Vec (Figure 10) and both graph embedding techniques (Figures 9 and 8). Each pair of submissions is represented by a coordinate on the heatmap (e.g. point (0,0) represents the similarity between submission 0 and itself). Each of the 10 submissions

³<https://github.com/tech-sr1/code2vec>

for a problem are sequential. The first 20 submissions correspond to Exercise 1 and Exercise 2, the last 20 correspond to Exercise 3 and Exercise 4.

3.6 Predicting Student Grades

To evaluate each embedding’s ability to capture information relevant to students’ performance, we trained Linear, Ridge, Lasso, and Neural regression models to predict students’ final exam grades on the train/test divided data using the 8 different types of embeddings extracted from their program submissions. We compared the CFG feature extraction technique against Code2Vec and term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) as two feature extraction baselines. To embed our CFGs, we used deepwalk (DW) and node2vec (N2V) using three different levels of canonicalization. Our levels of canonicalization were no canonicalization (NC), partial canonicalization (PC), and full canonicalization (FC).

3.6.1 Data Preprocessing

To create the student embeddings, we performed the following preprocessing. Students had the ability to submit many times to the same assignment. To create fixed-length vectors for every student, we represented their attempt at each problem as the embedding for their best submission, which was defined as the submission with the highest score. All of these embeddings were concatenated into a single vector for each student, representing their code for every assignment. For assignments that students did not submit or that we had no vectors for, a 0-vector was concatenated instead of the embedding. Since our feature space was larger than the number of students we had, we also fit a principal component analysis (PCA) model with every regression model to reduce the feature space.

3.6.2 Models

We trained the four models specified above to predict students’ final exam grades. We tuned the following hyperparameters on the training data using 5-fold cross-validation and a randomized search which checked 29 combinations of hyperparameters:

- # of Components (PCA)
 - 10, 20, 30, ..., 290
- Alpha
 - 1e-10, 1e-8, 1e-6, 1e-4, 1e-2, 1e-1, 1, 2, 5
- Hidden Layer Sizes
 - (128, 64, 32, 16), (128, 64, 32), (128, 64), (64, 32, 16), (64, 32), (32, 16, 8), (32, 16), (16, 8)

Table 1 shows the values for each parameter of the highest performing model for each embedding technique after tuning. Logistic sigmoid was used as the activation function for the neural network to constrain grades between 0 and 1.

3.6.3 Embeddings and Baselines

As previously mentioned, we compared two graph embedding techniques, DeepWalk and Node2Vec, against Code2Vec to predict students’ exam grades. We compared these three embedding techniques against two baseline methods.

	# PCA Com	Alpha	HL Sizes
code2vec - Neural	80	1e-1	(128,64)
TF-IDF - Lasso	40.0	1e-4	
FC-DW - Lasso	50.0	0e1	
FC-N2V - Neural	150	1e-6	(128,64)
FC-N2V - Lasso	50.0	1e-6	
PC-DW - Neural	230	1e-2	(128,64,32)
PC-N2V - Ridge	50.0	1e-6	
NC-DW - Linear	50.0		
NC-DW - Lasso	50.0	0e1	
NC-N2V - Lasso	50.0	0e1	

Table 1: Tuned Hyperparameter Values

The first method, mean grade prediction, simply predicts the mean grade from the training data. We chose this to ensure the embeddings outperform the most naive method possible.

The second method, term frequency-inverse document frequency, was chosen as a naive feature extraction technique for the programs. TF-IDF does not utilize any syntactic or semantic information from the programs, but instead tracks frequencies for the tokens in the program text. We chose this method to test our performance against an unsophisticated feature extraction.

With the exception of mean grade prediction, each regression model was trained with each of the four feature extraction techniques.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Program Similarity

Figures 8, 9, and 10 show the program similarity heat maps for our three highest performing models when calculating program similarity, as described in Section 3.5. The top three in order were Code2Vec, PC - DeepWalk, and PC - Node2Vec. From the heatmaps, we can see that Code2Vec outperforms DeepWalk and Node2Vec at showing similarity between assignments as well as similarity within assignments. We believe this is because Code2Vec was explicitly created to capture *relationships* between programs, whereas our method utilizes sums of vectors capturing relationships between *graph nodes*. Despite our methods failing to outperform Code2Vec, the results shown are evidence that the techniques are capturing inter and intra assignment similarity.

4.2 Final Grade Prediction

Table 2 details the performance of each of the seven embedding types compared with the two baselines when the models are used on the testing set. The mean grade was not used in conjunction with any models because it does not take into account any features. Our results show that Code2Vec outperforms both the mean grade and the TF-IDF models. However, the graph embedding methods outperform Code2Vec by approximately 7%. This supports our hypothesis that the inclusion of semantic information improves the accuracy of student performance modeling, even when using naive graph embedding techniques such as DeepWalk and Node2Vec, which use far less sophisticated techniques than Code2Vec.

Figure 7: An ideal heatmap where the darker the color the closer together the program vectors

Figure 8: A heatmap showing the similarity between assignments when using node2vec and partial canonicalization for embedding

Figure 9: A heatmap showing the similarity between assignments when using deepwalk partial canonicalization for embedding

Figure 10: A heatmap showing the similarity between assignments when using code2vec for embedding

The 2nd CSEDM data challenge winners ⁴ hosted on CodaLab [18] successfully managed to predict grades within-semester with an RMSE of 0.127 when adjusting the scores to the same scale that we used. Without using any data other than the control flow graphs, we were able to get within 0.057 of their results.

Embedding	Regression	MAE	RMSE
None	Mean	0.188	0.235
TF-IDF	Lasso	0.177	0.214
Code2Vec	Neural	0.153	0.197
NC-Node2Vec	Lasso	0.149	0.195
NC-DeepWalk	Linear	0.150	0.193
FC-DeepWalk	Lasso	0.143	0.187
PC-Node2Vec	Ridge	0.142	0.186
FC-Node2Vec	Neural	0.143	0.186
PC-DeepWalk	Neural	0.142	0.184

Table 2: The MAE and RMSE for the regression model with the lowest RMSE for that particular embedding technique

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Research Question #1

To evaluate our first research question, "Can embeddings of control-flow graphs capture program features in an educational context?", we generated similarity heatmaps for similar and dissimilar assignments. We found that the similarity between similar assignments was higher than it was between dissimilar assignments and it was even higher between solutions to the same assignment. However, it did not outperform Code2Vec. The Code2Vec model is more well-designed to encode differences and similarities in programs because it includes word embedding information from method and variable names. This could mean that our technique needs some additional ways to identify relevant semantics and not just all semantics.

Some possibilities for improving the program similarity identification includes: adding an attention mechanism to the training method for embedding the graphs to ensure that the most important features are embedded and integrating flow data directly into the embeddings such that the direction of flow and type of nodes is part of the paths as well.

⁴<https://competitions.codalab.org/competitions/33164#results>

5.2 Research Question #2

To evaluate our second research question, "Can embeddings created from control-flow graphs outperform AST-based methods in predicting grades?", we attempted to predict final grades by feeding the embeddings into multiple regression models. From our results, we found that we were able to outperform both the mean grade baseline, the TF-IDF baseline, and code2vec. We believe this is because our embeddings more accurately capture correct usage of certain concepts (such as loops) than code2vec can with it's usage of ASTs.

An interesting sub-question that arose out of the previous RQ is the impact of canonicalization on our embeddings. The results that we have, show a mild improvement in performance from the partially canonicalized graphs over the non-canonicalized and fully-canonicalized. This makes sense with the understanding that most of us have with the purpose of literals in our code. Values in the program serve a specific purpose and often significantly impact the functionality of programs. Particularly if they are constants. On the other hand, the non-canonicalized doing worse than the partially canonicalized also tells us that variable names can obfuscate the meaning of the code with the techniques that we are using to embed the graphs. Such impact suggests that further research is necessary for the impact of canonicalization in the usage of our technique. However, this may also be mitigated through the usage of an attention mechanism to identify relevant parts of the statements.

5.3 Conclusions

Altogether, our results are promising indicators of the efficacy of embeddings of control-flow graphs in capturing information about students' programming relevant to their performance. Furthermore, they indicate that the inclusion of data about the logical flow of statements in the program can outperform AST-based methods at the task of predicting student performance.

5.4 Limitations

First, the dataset impacted our ability to evaluate the technique's performance. The final exam grades which we were predicting had a narrow distribution (standard deviation of 0.24) which made a difficult task all the more difficult. Also, the amount of data was extremely limited and meant that our embeddings, when concatenated, led to vectors with a greater number of features than our number of students, which led to the necessity for feature reduction.

Second, the technique that we used to generate all of the control-flow graphs, while able to handle most common cases for students in a CS1 course, is not able to represent any methods that include exception-based control flow or lambda expressions.

Finally, the adapted graph embedding techniques we used do not consider any of the flow data indicating the direction of flow for a decision node available on the edges in the CFGs. Instead, we can only get some of that information from the paths that we generate. However, it still does not include the explicit direction indicators available in the edge data.

5.5 Future Work

This tool with some extension could aid in better extracting student knowledge state while they are programming. Integration with intelligent tutoring systems and other tools for use in the classroom could give better indication of student understanding of programming constructs. This would allow teaching staff or automated systems to provide more individualized help with concepts that a student is struggling to understand. The results and limitations discussed throughout the paper lead to several possible extensions to build to this type of tooling.

First, the limitations with the CFG generation technique give rise to several possible extensions. The number of programs we were unable to convert into control-flow graphs for use in training means that extending the control-flow graph generator to be able to handle exception-based control flow and lambda control flow is critical to handling computer science course data. Another extension that is promising is the ability of control flow graphs to represent entire student projects in a way that an AST cannot. With this, we could embed a student's entire program graph providing an overview of their program that would be nigh impossible to get from an AST.

Second, while our results support that the CFG embedding technique outperforms at least one AST-based technique, if we embed abstract syntax trees using the graph embedding techniques, we can confirm whether the benefit of our technique arises out of the graph embedding techniques utilized or the control-flow graphs being generated. This would allow us to more directly weigh the benefit of using control-flow graphs over ASTs and possibly make another set of techniques available for integration in instruction.

Third, to further evaluate and improve the performance of this technique for use in tooling, other prediction tasks should be utilized. A larger dataset with better KCs, more submissions, and more types of prediction tasks is the ideal way to evaluate this technique more accurately and determine the strengths and weaknesses of this technique. Then, this technique should be extended with other graph embedding techniques, such as graph neural networks [22], LINE [28], and struc2vec [21]. Finally, we should compare the CFG embedding to other AST-based embedding techniques such as ast2vec [17] or the path-based representation from Alon et al. [4].

Finally, we believe more investigation of our research questions is precipitated by our results. Firstly, our code sim-

ilarity analysis is done using only four assignments, with no gold standard to evaluate its performance. Future work could involve manually scoring similarity between each assignment and calculating the difference between the similarity estimated by euclidean distance and the manual similarities. Along with graph embeddings of ASTs, we can also evaluate our embedding methods using more sophisticated regression models such as deep learning models, sequential models, and combined architectures and more sophisticated feature extraction techniques, such as knowledge component (KC) extraction.

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